

THE INFLUENCE OF SOLAR SPECTRUM ON OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF PRINTED EFFECT PIGMENTS

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Abstract: In this study, the influence of the entire solar spectrum, including the ultraviolet (UV), visible (VIS), and near infrared (NIR) regions, on the transmission and reflectance of printed effect pigments on OPP film was investigated. Five different commercially available effect pigments from Merck (Germany) were used, which differ in their pigment shape, chemical composition, pigment color and particle size. The results show that all the pigments analysed have the lowest transmission in the UV region, which then gradually increases with increasing wavelength, meaning that the values in the NIR region were the highest. In addition, the largest deviations in the reflectance spectra were found for the pigments EP1 and EP5 in the UV region. In the VIS region, the reflectance increased for all pigments and fell slowly in the NIR region. Among the pigments analyzed, pigment EP3 achieved the lowest overall transmission, whereas EP2 exhibited the lowest reflectance across the entire solar spectrum.

Keywords: effect pigments, solar spectrum, transmission, reflectance

1 INTRODUCTION

In space, the solar spectrum is more like the radiation of a black body and covers different wavelengths. On the Earth, Sunlight is scattered in specific infrared, visible, and ultraviolet (UV) light rays. The composition of the solar spectrum includes 52% NIR radiation (700-2500 nm), 43% visible (VIS) light (400-700 nm), and 5% ultraviolet (UV) radiation (100-400 nm). The infrared radiations account for more than half of the solar radiations (Mansour et al., 2025, La Notte et al., 2020). The UV radiation is further divided into: UV-C (100-280 nm, which is generally created from artificial light sources), UV-B (280-315 nm, being the most energetic component of natural UV light), UV-A (315-400 nm, which accounts for the lowest energy of UV light) (Roy et al., 2023).

Figure 1: The solar spectrum.

UV-light is known for its negative impact on human health. It causes sun burns, eye damages, accelerated skin ageing and skin cancer. Beside these health issues, the protection against UV-light is often also required for material protection, e.g. for improvement of the light fastness. IR-light is also named as heat radiation and for this the protection against IR-light is often related to heat regulation and heat management (Greiler et al., 2021).

In cases of surfaces exposed to Sunlight, solar energy can be transmitted, reflected, or absorbed. When the frequency of the incoming light is near to the electron energy levels of a sun-exposed material, the electrons will absorb the light wave energy and the electrons' energy state changes. In other words, the absorbed light is converted into thermal energy. The absorption of light depends on the nucleus and on electrons. In its transmission, light moves through a substrate, and at the reflection of different wavelengths, the angle of incidence of the light is equal to that of the reflection on smooth surfaces; consequently, the light bounces back from the surface (Mara et al., 2023).

Apart from the visible region, effect pigments also interact with other wavelengths of light in the electromagnetic spectrum (Bendiganavale et al., 2008). The class of effect pigments (luster pigments) comprises the two main groups of special effect pigments including pearl luster pigments (pearlescent pigments, nacreous pigments, interference pigments) and metal effect pigments (Buxbaum et al., 2005). All these pigments consist of small thin platelets that show strong lustrous effects when oriented in parallel alignment in application systems (e.g. in paints, plastics, printing inks, etc.) (Klein, 2010, Rossi et al., 2020). Pearlescent pigment is a kind of optical effect pigment invented by imitating the principle of pearl formation. The core is a micron-sized mica sheet or other substrates, and the surface can be coated with multi-layer nano-scale metal or non-metal oxide film. The pigment is colored on the base of light interference effect. As the white light shines on the surface of the pearlescent pigment sheet, it exhibits a variety of bright colors through multiple reflection and refraction of light (Yang et al., 2024).

Figure 2 shows the various optical principles of conventional pigments (absorption pigments), metallic pigments, natural pearl as well as pearl lustre pigments.

Figure 2: Optical properties of A) absorption pigments; B) metal effect pigments; C) natural pearl; D) pearl lustre pigments.

In the case of absorption pigments, the interaction with light is based upon absorption and/or diffuse scattering. A completely different optical behaviour can be observed with the group of effect pigments including pearl lustre and metal effect pigments. Metal effect pigments consists of small metal platelets (for example aluminium, titanium, copper) which operate like mirrors and almost completely reflect the incident light. Pearl lustre pigments are natural or synthetic pigments and the visual impression develops by reflection and scattering of light on thin multiple layers. The visual impression develops by reflection and scattering of light on thin multiple layers (Fig. 2D) (Buxbaum et al., 2005, Glausch et al., 1998).

In recent years, there have been several studies on solar spectral optical properties of pigments. Yang et al. investigate VO₂ nano-rod coated mica composites pearlescent pigment for temperature control packaging (Yang et al., 2024). In the study conducted by Alkan et al., iron oxide particles with promising energy storage properties were investigated as new solar heat absorber and storage medium candidates (Alkan et al, 2023). Furthermore, in the study conducted by Toy, E. et al., the effect of particle size on color and NIR reflectivity of (Fe,Cr)₂O₃ black pigment was investigated (Toy, E. et al., 2025).

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, five different commercially available effect pigments from Merck (Germany) were used, which were printed on transparent OPP film using the gravure printing process. The pigments differed in their pigment shape, chemical composition, pigment's color and particle size. Three pigments (EP1, EP2, EP3) are mica-based pigments, two pigments (EP4, EP5) are silica-based pigments (Table 1). Oriented polypropylene (OPP) is a polypropylene plastic film that is oriented in two directions for added strength.

Table 1: Properties of effect pigments

Pigment label	Trade name	Form	Chemical composition	Pigment color	Particle size
EP1	Iriodin® 123	Powder	Mica: 60-68 % Titanium Dioxide: 32-39 % Tin Oxide: < 1 %	White	5 - 25 μm
EP2	Iriodin® 305	Powder	Mica + Silicon Dioxide: 45-66 % Titanium Dioxide: 19-29 % Iron Oxide: 15-25 % Tin Oxide: 1 %	Yellow	10 - 60 μm
EP3	Iriodin® 520	Powder	Mica: 53-58 % Iron Oxide: 42-47 %	Orange	5 - 25 μm
EP4	Colorstream® T10-02	Powder	Silicon Dioxide: 57-68 % Titanium Dioxide: 30-39 % Tin Oxide: 2-4 %	Turquoise / Silver / Red / Gold	5 - 50 μm
EP5	Colorstream® T10-04	Powder	Silicon Dioxide: 72-84 % Titanium Dioxide: 14-24 % Tin Oxide: 2-4 %	Gold / Silver / Green / Blue	5 - 50 μm

A Scanning Electron Microscope - SEM (JSM-5610JOEL) was used to evaluate the pigment particles. The transmission (T) and reflectance (R) spectra of the printed pigments were obtained with Lambda 950 UV-VIS-NIR spectrometer (PerkinElmer, USA) in the range of wavelengths from 250 nm to 2000 nm, at 10-nm intervals.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 shows a scanning electron microscope (SEM) micrographs of pigments based on a) mica flakes (EP1) and b) silica flakes (EP4) at 1000x magnification. In both pigments examined (EP1 and EP4), the "corn flake" morphology is clearly recognisable, in which the particles appear as thin, irregular flakes with sharp edges and relatively smooth surfaces.

Figure 3: Scanning electron micrographs of pigments based on mica flakes (EP1) and b) silica flakes (EP4).

The transparent mica flakes are coated on all sides with a thin layer of metal oxide, mostly titanium dioxide. The presence of a highly refractive and reflective surface layer covering the less refractive support material results in a significant pearlescent effect and provides colours resulting from light interference. The carrier material of Colorstream® multicolor effect pigments (EP4, EP5) is synthetically produced silicon dioxide (SiO₂). Coated with highly refractive metal oxides, the wafer-thin and smooth platelets reflect the light and create extraordinary, changing interference colours (Maile et al., 2005). The transmission through a coating containing effect pigments is influenced by two effects the absorption of the pigment and interference effects (Greiler, 2021).

The Figure 4 shows the optical transmission spectra of five printed pigments (EP1-EP5) on transparent film, measured with a UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer across the wavelength range from 250 to 2000 nm. The spectra are divided into three main regions: UV (250-400 nm), VIS (400-700 nm), NIR (700-2000 nm). All pigments show the lowest transmission in the UV region compared to VIS and NIR regions, indicating strong absorption or scattering, which provides UV-shielding properties. In the visible region, the transmission spectra vary strongly among the pigments, with pigments EP4 and EP5, having a higher transmittance, while pigment EP3 has the lowest. In the NIR region, most pigments tend toward higher transmission (>70%), suggesting they allow infrared light to pass through while still modifying visible appearance. The pigment EP3 exhibits the lowest transmittance in the entire solar spectrum.

Figure 4: Transmission spectra of printed pigments on OPP film in the UV-VIS-NIR regions.

Infrared reflective pigments, such as titanium dioxide (TiO₂) powder, exhibit significant visible opacity. This means such pigments primarily scatter or transmit the infrared radiation. On the other hand, thin

films are not proficient in scattering or reflecting all infrared radiation, which allows a portion of this radiation to penetrate to the substrate (Mansour et al., 2025).

The Figure 5 presents in more detail the transmission spectra in UV region (the wavelength range from 250 to 400 nm).

Figure 5: Transmission spectra of printed pigments on OPP film in the UV-A, UV-B and UV-C regions.

The pigment EP3 shows high UV-shielding properties in whole UV region with <10 % transmission. As shown in Table 1, the pigment EP3 contains 53-58 % mica and 42-47 % iron oxide. Silica or mica are almost transparent materials for light. However, metal oxide like titania or iron oxide absorb UV-light and can for this decrease the transmission in the spectral area of UV-light (Greiler, 2021). Similar values was noticed for pigment EP1, except in the UV-A region, where the transmission increased. The highest transmittance was noticed for pigment EP2 (chemical composition: mica + silicon dioxide: 45-66 %, titanium dioxide: 19-29 %, iron oxide: 15-25 %, tin oxide: 1 %), where the values was higher than 40%.

Figure 6 shows that the reflectance is relatively different between the pigments. The pigments EP2, EP3 and EP4 have a low reflectance in the UV range, which indicates a high UV absorption. The pigments EP1 and EP5 have a higher reflectance compared to the others. For the pigment EP1, the peak value R at 285 nm is around 75 % and decreases in the VIS and NIR range. In the visible range (400-700 nm), the highest R values were found for pigment EP1, where the peak value R at 420 nm was 67 %. In the NIR range, pigment EP3 has the highest reflectance.

Figure 6: Reflectance spectra of printed pigments on OPP film in the UV-VIS-NIR regions.

As shown in Figure 7, the pigments EP2, EP3, and EP4 exhibit low reflectance (<25%) in the entire UV region, indicating strong UV absorption in the deep UV region. The pigment EP5 has the highest reflectance (~73%) in UV-C and UV-B regions, while the pigment EP1 in the UV-A region (~57%).

Figure 7: Reflectance spectra of printed pigments on OPP film in the UV-A, UV-B and UV-C regions.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrated that the transmittance and reflectance of printed effect pigments on OPP film are strongly dependent on wavelength of light and pigment characteristics. All pigments exhibited the lowest transmission in the UV region, which increased toward the NIR region, while reflectance showed a rising trend in the VIS region and a gradual decline in the NIR region. Among the pigments analyzed, pigment EP3 achieved the lowest overall transmittance, whereas EP2 exhibited the lowest reflectance across the entire solar spectrum. These findings provide valuable insights for optimizing pigment selection in applications requiring controlled optical properties under entire spectrum solar exposure.

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